

A new species of the genus *Obrium* Dejean, 1821 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from Mongolia

Maxim A. LAZAREV¹ & Richard AMBRUS²

¹Free Economic Society of Russia,
Department of Scientific Conferences and All-Russian Projects
Bolshaya Tatarskaya str., 35, build. 3, Moscow 115184 Russia
e-mail: humanityspace@gmail.com, cerambycidae@bk.ru; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4040-0987>

²Trnkovo nám. 1112/1, CZ-152 00 Praha 5, Czech Republic
e-mail: ambrus@centrum.cz

Taxonomy, new species, Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Obriini, *Obrium*, Mongolia

Abstract. A new species, *Obrium purcharti* sp. nov. from Mongolia (Khovd aimag) is described. It is compared with close *O. cantharinum* (Linnaeus, 1767). Distinguishing characters and color photos of specimens are proposed.

INTRODUCTION

Detailed lists of Mongolian Cerambycidae were published in a series of articles by Namhaidorz (1972, 1974, 1976, 1979, 1982). But no species of *Obrium* Dejean, 1821 were known to him on the basis of his own materials. *Obrium cantharinum* (Linnaeus, 1767) was mentioned for Mongolia by Heyrovský (1968): “Chovd aimak: Mongol Altaj Gebirge, Uljasutajn gol, 45 km NNO von Somon Bulgan, 1400 m, 6.-7.7.1966 (Nr. 639), 1 Ex.”. No other specimens of the genus for Mongolia were ever published. Most probably the specimen published by Heyrovský (1968) belongs to the new species, which is described below.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Canon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Acronyms of collections:

ML collection of M. A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia);
RA collection of R. Ambrus (Praha, Czech Republic).

RESULT

***Obrium purcharti* sp. nov.** (Figs. 1-2)

Type material. Holotype (♂): Mongolia [M 25], 22 km N of Buglan, 46°17'27.496"N, 091°34'39.778"E, 1600 m, 23-25.6.2025, L. Purchart leg., (ML). Paratypes: (1 ♂, 2 ♀♀): with the same data as the holotype, (RA).

Figs. 1-4. *Obrium purcharti* sp. nov.: 1- Holotype, male (Photo by M. Lazarev); 2- Paratype, female (Photo by L. Purchart); *Obrium cantharinum cantharinum* (Linnaeus, 1767): 3- male, Moscow Region, Udelnaya, (Photo by M. Lazarev); 4- female, Moscow Region, Trudovaya, (Photo by M. Lazarev).

Description. Head, thorax, elytra and abdomen dark, reddish-brown, antennae and legs black; head shining, with moderately large punctation and thin scattered setae, frons transverse; eyes large, strongly convex, roughly faceted; male antennae longer than body, surpassing elytral apices by 2 joints, in females a little longer than elytra; 1st antennal joint about as long as 4th, longer than 3rd and much shorter than 5th; prothorax elongated, about 1.34 times longer than basal width; strongly tuberculate at lateral middle; about as wide anteriorly as posteriorly; pronotum with sparse scattered fine punctation and a few erect setae; scutellum glabrous, triangular; elytra about parallel-sided, about 2.5 times longer, than humeral width; narrowed at middle and slightly widened posteriorly, with small very dense punctation and nearly indistinct recumbent pubescence, rounded apically; femora distinctly clavate; 1st abdominal segment about as long as all others together; body length of males: 7.5-8.5 mm, width at humeri of males: 2.0-2.3 mm; body length of females: 7.4-7.6 mm, width at humeri of females: 2.0-2.1 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is close to *O. cantharinum* (Linnaeus, 1767) (Figs. 3-4), but the body color is much darker; the elytra a little shorter, about 2.3-2.5 times longer than basal width (*O. cantharinum* - about 2.4-2.7 times); elytral punctation denser and rougher; the distance between upper eye lobes about 1.4 times more than width of the 1st antennal joint (in *O. cantharinum* - about 1.3 times); 5th joint about 1.5 times longer than 3rd (in *O. cantharinum* - about 1.3 times).

Etymology. The new taxon is named after Luboš Purchart (Department of Forest Ecology, Mendel University in Brno, Czech Republic), a specialist in Tenebrionidae.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT. I am very grateful to Luboš Purchart (Department of Forest Ecology, Mendel University, Brno, Czech Republic) for collecting the type series.

REFERENCES

- HEYROVSKÝ L. 1968: 157. Cerambycidae IV. Ergebnisse der zoologischen Forschungen von Dr. Z. Kaszab in der Mongolei (Coleoptera). *Reichenbachia* 11(21): 235-238.
- NAMHAIDORZH B. 1972: On the fauna of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of the Mongolian People's Republic. In: *Insects of Mongolia. 1.* Leningrad, "Nauka", pp. 495-538. (in Russian)
- NAMHAIDORZH B. 1974: Addition to a list of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of Mongolia. In: *Insects of Mongolia. 2.* Leningrad, "Nauka", pp. 172-175. (in Russian)
- NAMHAIDORZH B. 1976: On the fauna of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of the Mongolian People's Republic, II. In: *Insects of Mongolia. 4.* Leningrad, "Nauka", pp. 202-216. (in Russian)
- NAMHAIDORZH B. 1979: Little-known longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from the Mongolian People's Republic. In: *Insects of Mongolia. 6.* Leningrad, "Nauka", pp. 90-93. (in Russian)
- NAMHAIDORZH B. 1982: New data on longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of the Mongolian People's Republic. In: *Insects of Mongolia. 8.* Leningrad, "Nauka", pp. 294-295. (in Russian)

Received: 18.11.2025

Accepted: 10.12.2025

Printed: 31.3.2026